

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228823260>

Investigation of the performance of EP-BAVP (evolutionary programming for virtual path bandwidth allocation)

Conference Paper · January 1998

CITATIONS

6

READS

24

5 authors, including:

Andreas Pitsillides
University of Cyprus

302 PUBLICATIONS 3,025 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

C. S. Pattichis
University of Cyprus

431 PUBLICATIONS 5,676 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Georgios Stylianou
European University Cyprus

28 PUBLICATIONS 288 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Ahmet Sekercioglu
Monash University (Australia)

111 PUBLICATIONS 2,212 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

3D Face Reconstruction from a single Image [View project](#)

mEducator [View project](#)

INVESTIGATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF EP-BAVP (EVOLUTIONARY PROGRAMMING FOR VIRTUAL PATH BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION)

A. Pitsillides¹, C. S. Pattichis¹, G. Stylianou¹, A. Sekercioglu², T. Vassilakos³

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus, email:{cspitsil}
{pattichi}@turing.cs.ucy.ac.cy

²School of Computer Science and Software Engineering, Swinburne University of Technology,
Melbourne, Australia, email: ASekerci@swin.edu.au

³Institute of Computer Science, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas, (FORTH), Crete,
Greece, e-mail:
vasilako@csi.forth.gr

ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate the usefulness of an evolutionary programming (EP) optimization algorithm for tackling the problem of Bandwidth Allocation for Virtual Paths (EP-BAVP). Results for two network topologies obtained with EP are in close agreement with those obtained using a classical constrained optimization (CCO) technique. In the simplest topology (3 nodes) the EP algorithm achieves the same throughputs as the CCO, and converges to the solution within 100 generations, compared to the CCO technique, which converges in 50 iterations. In the more complex topology (4 nodes), the EP algorithm converges within 2000 generations, and the results are very close to the CCO solution which converges in 300 iterations. However, slightly higher throughputs (about 0.5%) were allocated by the classical technique. Furthermore, a similar time span was required for both algorithms for convergence for the 3 and 4 node problems. Our preliminary results suggest that it is worthwhile to obtain further insight into the reported strength of EP-BAVP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Broadband-ISDN's will support various classes of multimedia traffic with different bit rates and quality of service requirements, thus traffic control and resource management are crucial in order to guarantee the desired grade of service. Several mechanisms will exist in a Broadband-ISDN to allocate resources and control traffic, such as bandwidth allocation, buffer management, call admission control, input rate regulation, routing, and queue scheduling. It has been suggested that these controls will be applied at different levels in the network such as cell level, burst level, connection (i.e. call) level, Virtual Path (VP) level, and the network level.

In this paper we focus on the bandwidth allocation problem aimed at the VP and network levels, and investigate the usefulness of an evolutionary programming (EP) optimization algorithm in the problem of Bandwidth Allocation for Virtual Paths (EP-BAVP). We consider two network topologies (3 and 4 nodes) and compare the results with those obtained using a classical constrained optimization technique (CCO). The motivation behind the use of EP in nonlinear function optimization problems is that natural evolution provides an attractive paradigm for implementing a general nonlinear search [i][ii].

In an earlier paper [iii], we reported on the use of EP for the solution of the Bandwidth Allocation problem for Virtual Paths (BAVP). In [ii] we compared EP with a classical approach for a 3 node problem and showed that the EP approach achieves the same throughput for the case of the sum and the product of the objective functions. In this paper, we extend the problem to the 4-node case and investigate further the behaviour of the EP algorithm compared to the CCO approach.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2 we outline the problem formulation, and in section 3 the EP method is presented. In section 4 the 3 node and 4 node problems are presented, and the solutions offered by the classical and EP methods are discussed. Finally, in section 5 we present our conclusions.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND SOLUTION APPROACHES

EP-BAVP aims to supply optimal bandwidth (capacity, service-rate) assignment to VPs, taking into account global network considerations. It is located at the higher levels of the control structure; the VP and network

levels. It is therefore associated with a "slow" time scale in terms of minutes or tens of minutes. The model for Multiobjective BAVP was presented in [iii]. It uses a network carrier viewpoint and maximises total network throughput, with fairness among the bandwidth allocated to the VPs. Here we present the problem for a single objective function that of the sum of the individual objective functions for each VP.

A. BAVP model

Consider a (virtual) network consisting of N nodes representing ATM switches, and L transmission links connecting the nodes. For given: network topology; expected OD traffic loads; and link capacities, we try to find an optimal VP bandwidth assignment that maximises the total expected network throughput.

We define:

C_i^{link} - Available bandwidth of link i , $i=1, \dots, L$ for VP assignment.

N_p - Number of network unidirectional OD pairs, indexed $j = 1, \dots, N_p \leq N(N-1)$.

P_j - Number of predetermined possible paths connecting OD pair j (allows for multiple VPs between an OD pair).

$U_{j,p}$ - Bandwidth assigned to OD pair j through path p , $j = 1, \dots, N_p$, $p = 1, \dots, P_j$.

U_j - Bandwidth assigned to OD pair j . Clearly $U_j = \sum_{p=1}^{P_j} U_{j,p}$, $j = 1, \dots, N_p$.

$D_j(U_j)$ - Expected throughput of OD pair j when it utilises bandwidth assignment of size U_j (typically a concave non-decreasing function).

$T_j^{\min} (T_j^{\max})$ - Minimal (maximal) bandwidth assigned by the user to OD pair j (e.g. T_j^{\min} can be set to meet minimum performance objectives and T_j^{\max} for fairness).

$d_{j,p}^i$ - a (0,1) indicator variable which takes the value of 1 if path p of OD pair j uses link i .

$F_j(U_j)$ ($f_j(u)$) - probability (density) function for bandwidth demand.

The mathematical formulation for such a model is :

$$\max_U \left(\sum_i D_i(U_i) \right) \quad (1)$$

subject to the constraints

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \sum_{p=1}^{P_j} d_{j,p}^i U_{j,p} \leq C_i^{link}, \quad i = 1, \dots, L$$

$$T_j^{\min} \geq U_j = \sum_{p=1}^{P_j} U_{j,p} \geq T_j^{\max} \quad j = 1, \dots, N_p$$

$$U_{j,p} \geq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, N_p \quad p = 1, \dots, P_j.$$

To solve the above model, statistical characteristics of the functions $D_j(U_j)$, $j = 1, \dots, N_p$ should be known.

We assume that each function $D_j(U_j)$ is derived from an appropriate probability function $F_j(U_j)$ for bandwidth demand and a corresponding probability density function $f_j(u)$. By considering the throughput as a "fluid flow", the function $D_j(U_j)$ can be obtained [iii, iv]:

$$\begin{aligned} D_j(U_j) &= \int_0^{U_j} u f_j(u) du + U_j \int_{U_j}^{\infty} f_j(u) du = \\ &= \int_0^{U_j} u f_j(u) du + U_j [1 - F_j(U_j)] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The first term in equation (2) is the expected throughput for bandwidth demand below the assigned bandwidth of U_j , and the second term is for demand above the assigned bandwidth of U_j . In [iv], we show that the expected throughput decreases, as variance of bandwidth demand (derived from normal probability) increases.

B. Solution approach

In this paper an EP optimisation technique is applied in the problem of bandwidth allocation. EP facilitates an efficient nonlinear function optimization paradigm. We want to exploit the reported strength of EP to gain further insight into the problem of BAVP. Note that similar techniques to EP are evolutionary strategies [ii], and genetic algorithms (GA) [v], [vi]. These techniques share many similarities. Each maintains a population of trial solutions, imposes random changes to those solutions, and incorporates selection to determine which solutions to maintain into future generations, and which to remove from the pool of trials. However, these techniques have important differences. GAs emphasize models of genetic operators as observed in nature, such as crossing-over, inversion, and point mutation, and apply these usually to binary coded chromosomes. On the other hand, evolutionary strategies and evolutionary programming emphasize mutational transformations that maintain behavioral linkage between each parent and its offspring, respectively at the level of the individual or the species [ii]. There are not many published works in the area of

communication networks that make use of EP or GAs. Notable exceptions include [vii], [viii].

III. METHOD

A. Evolutionary programming function optimization

In this study the Genetic Algorithm for Numerical Optimization for Constraint Problems (GENOCOP) was implemented as follows [ii]:

1. The algorithm processed and eliminated if possible some of the constraints of the problem.
2. A total of 30 real valued vectors, $U_i, i = 1, \dots, 30, (P = 30)$ were initialized at random.
3. All vectors, $U_i, i = 1, \dots, 30$, were scored with respect to the selected function $F(U)$:

$$\text{Max}\left\{\sum_i D_i(U_i)\right\}$$

3. A group of members of the population was selected to reproduce and a group was selected to die.
4. Genetic operators were applied and a new generation was produced to replace the members that died.
5. During reproduction a genetic operator was selected randomly to be applied and a vector or two vectors from the population were selected randomly to reproduce, until all the members that died were replaced.

The process was repeated to step 2 until a predetermined number of generations were evaluated.

IV. RESULTS

We consider two topologies for evaluating the two optimization methods: a 3 node network and a 4 node network.

Topology A: 3-node network, 2 OD pairs, 4 VPs

In [iii], we studied a 3-node network ($N=3$) with 2 OD pairs, both destined for node 3. Two VPs were established for each OD pair ($N_p=4, P_j=2, j=1,2$). The link capacities were set equal to 100 Mbit/sec ($C_i^{link} = 100, i=1,2,3$).

The network topology is shown in Figure 1, and the traffic characteristics (assuming a normally distributed probability function for bandwidth demand) are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 1. Three node network topology used for example 1.

OD pair	VP	μ	σ
1-3	$VP_{1,1}$ link 1,3	110	55
	$VP_{1,2}$ link 1,2,3		
2-3	$VP_{2,1}$ link 2,3	50	25
	$VP_{2,2}$ link 2,1,3		

Table 1. Traffic characteristics for example 1.

For both optimization techniques studied, the traffic demand shown in Table 1 is considered. It depicts traffic with low variance for both OD pairs ("smooth" traffic). (In [iii] other traffic profiles, such as "bursty" traffic were also considered). Table 2 shows the sum of the objective functions for each case for the CCO and EP methods.

For the 3-node problem there was exact agreement between CCO and GENOCOP algorithms. Convergence of the CCO algorithm was within 50 iterations, whereas convergence for the GENOCOP algorithm was achieved within 5 generations (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Convergence of the GENOCOP algorithm for the 3-node and 4-node network. Best score was equal to a constant, k , minus the sum of the objective functions. For the 3 and 4 node problems, k was set to 200 and 360, respectively.

Furthermore, the performance of the GENOCOP algorithm was investigated by varying the following parameters: number of parents, selective pressure, non-uniform

mutation, and simple crossover. The term selective pressure expresses the probability of chromosomal selection compared to the average probability of the population. It was observed that variations in these parameters do not affect the performance.

Topology B: 4-node network, 12 OD pairs, 24 VPs

In topology B, see network topology in Figure 3, we studied a 4-node network ($N=4$) with 12 OD pairs.

Figure 3. Four-node network topology used for example 2.

Two VPs were established for each OD pair ($N_p=24, P_j=2, j=1,2$). The link capacities were set equal to 120 Mbit/sec ($C_i^{link}=120, i=1,2,3,4,5$). The OD pairs are shown in Table 3. Note that most VP1 paths are single hop, and all VP2 paths are 2 hop. The traffic characteristics (assuming a normally distributed probability function for bandwidth demand) for a low variance load are tabulated in Table 4.

For both the CCO and GENOCOP algorithms, similar findings were obtained. However, the throughput

computed by the classical method was slightly higher, by about 0.5%, than the one computed by the GENOCOP method. Convergence of the CCO algorithm was achieved within 300 iterations, whereas convergence of the GENOCOP algorithm was achieved within 2000 generations (see Figure 2).

The performance of the GENOCOP algorithm was also investigated by varying the following parameters: number of parents, selective pressure, non-uniform mutation, and simple crossover. It was observed that for a more complex problem, the selection of the parameters of the algorithm does not play an important role in achieving peak performance. For the parameter number of parents, the value of 30 gave the best score, whereas for the parameter selective pressure 0.1 was the best value. Furthermore, the parameters non-uniform mutation and simple crossover slightly affect the performance of the algorithm. The best values for non-uniform mutation and simple crossover were 6 and 10 respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the problem investigated, preliminary findings suggest that using EP a satisfactory solution to the problem of bandwidth allocation for Virtual Paths can be obtained. Both the CCO and GENOCOP algorithms gave similar solutions both for the 3 node and 4 node problems. Also, the GENOCOP algorithm demonstrated a robust performance in changes of its algorithmic parameters. Additionally, both algorithms achieved convergence at comparable time spans. Further work is currently in progress to explore completely the capacity of EP in multiobjective optimization bandwidth allocation problems.

Sum of the objective functions, $Max\{D_1(U_1) + D_2(U_2)\}$			
CLASSICAL		GENOCOP	
bandwidth allocations	objective function	bandwidth allocations	objective function
$U_1=137$ $U_2=63$	$D_1(U_1)=99$ $D_2(U_2)=45$	$U_1=137$ $U_2=63$	$D_1(U_1)=99$ $D_2(U_2)=45$

Table 2. Bandwidth allocations for a 3-node network using classical optimisation techniques in comparison to EP optimisation techniques.

VP1 path (links)	1-2	1-3	1-3, 3-4	2-1	2-3	2-4	3-1	3-2	3-4	4-3, 3-1	4-2	4-3
VP2 path (links)	1-3, 3-2	1-2, 2-3	1-2, 2-4	2-3, 3-1	2-1, 1-3	2-3, 3-4	3-2, 2-1	3-4, 4-2	3-2, 2-4	4-2, 2-1	4-3, 3-2	4-2, 2-3

Table 3: OD pairs; 2 VPs are set for each OD pair

OD pair	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Mean	10	30	60	30	25	45	30	20	40	50	10	25

Variance	50	25	35	30	40	20	40	45	30	10	65	15
----------	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----

Table 4: Traffic demands (low variance) for 4-node network

Sum of objective functions, $\text{Max}\{D_1(U_1)+D_2(U_2)+\dots+D_{12}(U_{12})\}$			
CLASSICAL		GENOCOP	
bandwidth allocations	objective function	bandwidth allocations	objective function
$U_1=33$	$D_1(U_1)=15$	$U_1=33$	$D_1(U_1)=15$
$U_2=38$	$D_2(U_2)=25$	$U_2=37$	$D_2(U_2)=25$
$U_3=39$	$D_3(U_3)=34$	$U_3=35$	$D_3(U_3)=33$
$U_4=43$	$D_4(U_4)=26$	$U_4=44$	$D_4(U_4)=26$
$U_5=60$	$D_5(U_5)=27$	$U_5=60$	$D_5(U_5)=27$
$U_6=50$	$D_6(U_6)=39$	$U_6=51$	$D_6(U_6)=39$
$U_7=43$	$D_7(U_7)=25$	$U_7=46$	$D_7(U_7)=26$
$U_8=60$	$D_8(U_8)=25$	$U_8=51$	$D_8(U_8)=22$
$U_9=50$	$D_9(U_9)=34$	$U_9=51$	$D_9(U_9)=34$
$U_{10}=44$	$D_{10}(U_{10})=42$	$U_{10}=45$	$D_{10}(U_{10})=42$
$U_{11}=26$	$D_{11}(U_{11})=13$	$U_{11}=27$	$D_{11}(U_{11})=13$
$U_{12}=31$	$D_{12}(U_{12})=22$	$U_{12}=31$	$D_{12}(U_{12})=22$
$\max_U \left(\sum_i D_i(U_i) \right) = 326$		$\max_U \left(\sum_i D_i(U_i) \right) = 324$	

Table 5. Bandwidth allocations for the 4 node network using classical optimisation techniques in comparison to EP optimisation techniques.

REFERENCES

- [i] Z. Michalewicz, "Genetic Algorithms + Data Structures = Evolution Programs", Third edition, Springer, Berlin, Germany, 1995.
- [ii] D.B. Fogel, "Evolutionary Computation", IEEE Press, NJ, USA, 1995.
- [iii] A. Pitsillides, C. Pattichis, A. Sekercioglu, A. Vassilakos "Bandwidth Allocation for Virtual Paths using Evolutionary Programming (EP-BAVP)", ICT'97, International Conference on Telecommunications, Melbourne, Australia, 2-4 April 1997.
- [iv] M. Herzberg, A. Pitsillides, "A hierarchical approach for the bandwidth allocation, management and control in B-ISDN", IEEE International Conference on Communications, ICC'93, Geneva, May 1993.
- [v] D. E. Goldberg, "Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization & Machine Learning", Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA, 1989.
- [vi] K.S. Tang, K.F. Man, S. Kwong, Q. He, "Genetic Algorithms and their Applications", IEEE Signal Processing, Vol. 13, No. 6, pp. 22-37.
- [vii] M. Markaki, A. Vasilakos, I. Kassotakis, "A hybrid genetic algorithm for an effective management of isochronous channels in high speed networks", IEEE International conference on Evolutionary Computation (ICEC'97), Purdue university, April 1997.
- [viii] R. Elbaum, M. Sidi, "Topological design of Local Area Networks using Generic Algorithms", IEEE/ACM

Transactions of Networking, Vol. 4, No. 5, October 1996.